

LEADERSHIP AND SELF-CARE

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ABSTRACT

This article is the result of a comparative analysis on the topic of Leadership and the need to take care of oneself, bringing a present contribution to the topic within ecclesiastical organizations. The contemporary Church has increasingly demanded more from leaders, both in the organizational, spiritual, emotional and other spheres of society. Being an effective leader involves not only technical skills and management abilities, but also the development of a healthy spirituality, ethical awareness and adequate self-care. The objective of this article refers to the process of self-management, in which the leader dedicates himself to improving his physical, mental and emotional well-being. This strategic practice seeks to promote the health and resilience of the leader, allowing him to perform his role more efficiently and healthily. There are several aspects of self-care that we could address, such as physical, mental and emotional health. In this article, we will only discuss the self-care that leaders need for their physical and emotional health, because if their emotions are sick, they will reflect on their exterior. So, how can they take care of people when they are sick? Their emotional and physical weakness can influence decision-making, communication, emotional intelligence, team engagement and compromise the outcome of the mission. As a result, we will examine different self-care approaches and strategies that can be adopted by leaders, including exercising, seeking a healthy work-life balance, cultivating meaningful relationships and developing self-reflection skills.

Keywords: Leadership. Care. Emotional. Mission.

INTRODUCTION

This study is a theological reinterpretation of leadership and self-care, based on the life and example of Jesus, the greatest leader in history, limited to Matthew 22:39. The work is the result of a comparative analysis on the theme of Leadership and the need to take care of oneself, bringing a present contribution to the theme within organizations, for the fulfillment of the mission.

The premise to be defended is that the mission, because it is from God, designates his interest in the integral reconciliation of the human being with himself (self-care), with God and with the world around him. In this sense, it is integral.

Organizations have increasingly demanded more from leaders, both in the organizational, spiritual, emotional and other spheres of society. Being an effective leader involves not only technical skills and management abilities, but also the development of a healthy spirituality, ethical awareness and adequate self-care.

Self-care refers to the process of self-management in which the leader dedicates himself to improving his physical, mental and emotional well-being. This strategic practice seeks to promote the health and resilience of the leader, allowing him to perform his role more efficiently and healthily.

There are several aspects of self-care that we could address, such as physical, mental and emotional health.

In this article, we will discuss self-care, which a leader needs to take care of his or her emotions, something beyond the external, including physical exercise, the search for a healthy balance between work and personal life, the cultivation of meaningful relationships and the development of self-reflection skills, because if your emotions are sick, they can reflect on your exterior, so how can you take care of people when you are sick? Your emotional weakness can influence decision-making, communication, emotional intelligence and team engagement, to accomplish the mission.

We believe that this study will provide important insights into the influence of self-care on leaders' performance and well-being, highlighting the importance of cultivating an emotional care approach to leadership. The knowledge gained may contribute to the implementation of effective leadership development strategies and the creation of healthy and productive organizational environments.

The Leader's humanity

“Leadership is the ability to influence people to work enthusiastically toward common goals, inspiring confidence through strength of character.” (HUNTER, 2004). Leadership is caring.

Hunter's comment points to the achievement of common goals, inspired by the leader as a person. I would like you to imagine the environment of constant decision-making processes and competitions in the day-to-day running of your organization, combined with the need to

always be presenting positive results of your workday. Our humanity, which is about characteristics and behaviors, becomes forgotten, in the face of these achievements; in many cases, we are like production machines prepared for positive results.

We need to relearn about our humanity as leaders and know that for a healthy spirituality, it will depend on how much of this humanity/limitation we have left, because our dehumanization implies distancing ourselves from the being that God created, for care, we are not production and result machines, leaders need to express their humanity, their mistakes, frustrations, disappointments, without fear or concern of losing their leadership, we need to understand that the more human we become, the more spiritual we will be.

In the book of Genesis chapter 1, verse 26: And God said, Let us make man in our image, after our likeness: and let them have dominion over the fish of the sea, and over the fowl of the air, and over the cattle, and over all the earth, and over every creeping thing that creepeth upon the earth. God confers upon man a special dignity, of “image and likeness.”

We are human, thanks be to God, we manifest the glory of God when we exercise care over God's creation, over our neighbors and especially when we take care of ourselves, exercising our humanity. All our love, all our creative capacity, our strength, our good deeds participate in this; they come from God and are present in humanity, as a gift that overflows from the creator to us, humans.

Exercising our humanity, then, would mean participating in the divine nature.

Care strategies that can be adopted by leaders

The practice of physical exercises

When we forget our humanity, or our limitations and start to play a role of superhumans in our leadership in relation to our activities, a false impression of productivity may occur, understanding that hours worked do not always reflect hours of production.

There is a popular saying that goes: Leisure is the father of creativity. I don't know who wrote it, but if we go around with our minds completely occupied with solving problems and tasks, there will really be little time left for leisure and little time for creativity.

Without these moments of rest, without these pauses for creativity, the mind and body cannot cope. Taking care of ourselves and remembering our humanity will keep us alive for a little longer. To forget this is to shorten our days on earth.

According to Kraemer, regular physical activity offers a wide range of benefits for the body and mind, including:

Cardiovascular health: Physical activity helps strengthen the heart, improve blood circulation and reduce the risk of heart diseases such as high blood pressure and coronary artery disease.

Weight control: Exercise helps burn calories and maintain a healthy weight.

Muscle and bone strengthening: Physical activity, such as weight training, Pilates or yoga, helps to strengthen muscles and bones, preventing loss of muscle mass and osteoporosis.

Improved mental health: Regular exercise releases endorphins, neurotransmitters responsible for providing a sense of well-being and reducing stress, anxiety and depression. In addition, it can also improve sleep and increase self-esteem.

Improved quality of life: Regular physical activity contributes to a healthier and more active life, improving quality of life and increasing longevity.

Remember, it is always important to consult a healthcare professional before starting any exercise program, especially if you have any pre-existing medical conditions.

The search for a healthy balance between work and personal life

Today we live in a time of hyperactivity, we arrange tasks, courses, cell phones, a state of continuous work that we affectionately call Home Office. Before, work was limited to an office that could operate from 8:00 am to 12:00 pm, or from 2:00 pm to 6:00 pm from Monday to Friday, but now we are taking work home, a virtual world that every day, traps us and takes us into a true space of “destruction”, destruction of personal relationships, valuing more and more the individuality of the human being, forgetting that our humanity is complete, when we manage to develop our self-awareness, to be able to stop these spaces of “destruction” in our personal lives.

Pastors and leaders must rest, because there will always be more tasks to be done when we get home, or within the organization. They need to be done, of course, but it is also perfectly acceptable to take a break from time to time, our humanity needs to be present. In Mark 4:35-41, it tells us that after a moment of teaching, Jesus withdraws with his disciples in a boat, and simply sleeps, rests.

Learn to leave less important things for later and enjoy your free time. Knowing how to rest when your body and mind ask for it is crucial to achieving a balance between work and personal life.

Identify your priorities both at work and in your personal life, family should always be a priority.

Determine what is most important to you and focus on those aspects.

Set clear boundaries between work and personal life (don't take work home). This may include setting specific times for using your cell phone, turning off your computer, avoiding responding to emails outside of work hours, and setting aside time for your personal activities.

Develop a weekly or daily plan to balance your professional and personal responsibilities. We are relational beings, we need others to live in community.

Learn to set boundaries and say "no" when necessary. Don't take on more tasks than you can successfully manage.

Maintain clear communication: Communicate with your employer, organizational members, coworkers, and loved ones about your needs and expectations regarding work-life balance.

Most importantly, be open to adjustments and be flexible to find what works best for you at different stages of your life.

Cultivating Meaningful Relationships

According to Boff (2014), by its nature, care includes two basic meanings, closely linked to each other. The first, the attitude of concern, solicitude and attention towards the other. The second, of concern and concern, because the person who is caring feels involved and emotionally connected to the other.

Contemporary society, recently called the knowledge and communication society, has created a lack of communication and vast loneliness among people, for example; the internet can connect us with millions of people without needing to meet someone, we buy, pay bills, work, order food, watch movies without necessarily having any kind of relationship.

The new virtual world has created a new habitat for human beings, characterized by self-encapsulation and a lack of touch.

According to (HOEKEMA, 1998 apud Rocha 2020), being a human being is being focused on one's fellow men, since the beginning man was formed to be a social being. The creation of woman is more than a sexual differentiation, it is the expression of man's need for companionship, he is not complete separated from others.

Community building is commonly referred to as the social mandate. It is only in partnership with others that we can fully develop our abilities and potential. This is true for all

human relationships. The construction of our identity lies in the building of community. Without it, we cannot be truly human.

The biblical principle of care indicates blessing, blessing and being blessed, loving and being loved, caring and being cared for. We are relational beings, in which every relationship of care means an action, love, not a feeling, but a behavior, being what we express in our relationships. Communication is the basis of any healthy relationship, be open to expressing your feelings honestly and also to listening carefully to what the other person has to say.

We manifest the glory of God when we exercise care over God's creation. Seek to understand and put yourself in the other person's shoes, show understanding, validate their feelings and be supportive in difficult times.

We were born to care. When I care, I reflect on others the existence of a God who cares about His creation. My humanity in relationships will be a seed that I will be harvesting in times of anguish and pain. If we stumble and fall, others will help us get back on our feet. Ecclesiastes chapter 4:9 says: Two are better than one, because they have a good return for their labor. For if one falls, the other will lift up his companion. But woe to him who is alone, for when he falls, there is no one to lift him up.

Dedicate time and attention to the people who are important to you, make plans together, talk, share memorable moments and be present in your life, don't be alone.

Forgive and let go, do not hold on to that which does not make your humanity flow, the ship was made for the high seas, but the moorings that tie it to the dock do not allow it to sail, release the moorings, understanding by moorings, that which does not let you be, what you were born to be, the image and likeness of a God who cares.

The development of self-reflection skills

This excessive hyperactivity, with the imperative to perform, can generate excessive demands and demands on leadership, which over time will turn the mission into a burden and not a purpose. This creates sick leaders, unable to lead, simply because they took care of others and did not take care of themselves. The pressure to perform ends up causing our humanity to be forgotten, making our leadership fragile.

The apostle Paul, after reviewing his ministry in Ephesus, counsels the leaders of the church in Acts 20:28: "Take heed therefore unto yourselves, and to all the flock, over the which the Holy Ghost hath made you overseers, to feed the church of God, which he hath purchased with his own blood." Note that their first concern and care is for themselves, and only then for

the flock of God. The exhortation is very clear: they cannot give proper care to the Lord's people, when they neglect the care and instruction of their own souls.

According to Rocha (2020), it is a big mistake to think that our mission is more important than our character. Jesus, before sending his disciples, addressed their character, John 13:20. Sanctification precedes work, character comes before mission, our intimacy with Christ must be more important than our work for Christ. According to (CHEYNE, apud Rocha 2020): "The life of a minister is the life of his ministry. To a large extent, success will occur according to the purity and perfections of the instrument. It is not great talents that God blesses, but the likeness to Jesus. A holy minister is a powerful weapon in the hands of God". What the Church needs today is not machinery, nor new organizations or better methods, but men whom the Holy Spirit can use – men of prayer, men powerful in prayer. The Holy Spirit does not flow through methods but through men. It does not descend through machinery but upon men. It does not anoint plans but men – men of prayer. (BOUNDS,2010).

The preacher's most intense and sharp preaching must be himself, his life of intimacy with God, through prayer, must come before all things, being with God, will provide the necessary strength to remain standing and thus help others to stand up.

Your most difficult, delicate, laborious and complete work must be done by yourself, through prayer.

CONSIDERATIONS

The theology of care is a theological perspective that emphasizes the importance of care as a central practice in faith and religious life, addressing the individual's responsibility to manifest the glory of God through care, empathy and compassion for one another, as well as for creation and the world in general. Thus, this text proposes to establish the connection between theological reflection and spiritual, pastoral and social considerations in order to foster a culture of self-care.

This approach recognizes that care is part of God's character and that human beings are called to reflect this care in their interactions and relationships. It seeks to integrate the practical dimension of care with theology and spirituality, recognizing that care is an expression of faith.

This theological perspective highlights the importance of care as a way of living faith authentically and demonstrates how faith can shape people's actions and attitudes. It invites individuals and communities to adopt a posture of active care, seeking to create a more loving, just, and compassionate world. For care is also part of the integrality of the mission.

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